

Supporting information: Electrodeposited NiCoP cathode catalyst for membrane alkaline electrolysis of water

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Influence of the phosphorus concentration in a deposition solution on resulting catalyst properties

$C_{\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ / mol dm ⁻³	Areas with up to 8 at.% of P	Areas with 10-15 at.% of P	Areas with more than 20 at.% of P
0.3 M		Not present	
0.6 M			
0.9 M			
1.2 M			

Figure S1: Changes in surface morphology with respect to increasing concentration of NaPO₂H₂·H₂O in a deposition solution. Constant Ni:Co ratio of 0.5 in the deposition solution (NiCl₂·6H₂O (0.2 mol dm⁻³), CoCl₂·6H₂O (0.2 mol dm⁻³)).

The varying composition strongly influences the surface morphology of the prepared samples. Areas with varying P concentration and morphology are present even for the same initial concentration of $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the deposition solution. For the concentration of 0.3 mol dm^{-3} , the areas with phosphorus concentration higher than 9.3 at.% were not present. For SEM-EDS results value shown corresponds to the average value from at least four measurements performed at different positions.

Table S1: Elemental composition (At.%) of the $0.2\text{Ni}0.2\text{Co}z\text{P}$ ($z = 0.3, 0.6$ and 1.2) catalyst determined by SEM-EDS and XRF. Constant Ni:Co ratio of 0.5 in the deposition solution ($\text{NiCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.2 mol dm^{-3}), $\text{CoCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.2 mol dm^{-3})).

$C_{\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}} / \text{mol dm}^{-3}$	0.3		0.6		0.9		1.2	
	SEM-EDS (At.%)	XRF (At.%)						
Ni	39.70	48.62	42.44	47.46	40.19	46.26	36.31	46.11
Co	52.74	48.76	47.62	49.15	41.49	49.20	47.28	49.07
P	7.56	2.62	11.11	3.39	18.33	4.54	16.41	4.82

The XRF analysis shows a similar trend regarding the final composition of the catalyst. Differences in absolute values could be caused by the sensitivity of SEM-EDS to lighter elements, whereas XRF tends to be more sensitive to heavier elements.

Description of the evaluation of the elemental composition (at.%) by XPS

Figure S2: XPS survey spectrum of the electrodeposited $0.2\text{Ni}0.2\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$ catalyst. Deposition solution composition: $\text{NiCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.2 mol dm^{-3}), $\text{CoCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.2 mol dm^{-3}), and $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.6 mol dm^{-3}); -25 mA cm^{-2} , $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure S3: XPS analysis of the $0.2\text{Ni}0.2\text{Co}_z\text{P}$ catalyst with respect to increasing concentration of $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in a deposition solution ($z = 0.3, 0.6$ and 1.2) and Ni and Co concentrations 0.2 ml dm^{-3} for both (Ni:Co ratio of 0.5). A – Ni $2p_{3/2}$ spectra, B – Co $2p$ spectra, C – P $2p$ spectra, D – O $1s$ spectra; electrodeposition at -25 mA cm^{-2} , 25°C .

Initially, the peak areas of the corresponding elements are calculated. These areas are then adjusted using element-specific sensitivity factors to account for the varying photoelectron excitation of each element. Finally, the relative atomic concentrations are calculated by comparing the normalised peak areas, providing insights into the elemental composition of the sample surface.

As XPS analysis is more surface-specific, with depth resolution of up to 20 nm compared to units of μm for SEM-EDS. The higher concentration of phosphorus detected by this method may indicate its increased concentration in the catalyst surface layer.

Table S2: Elemental composition (At.%) of the $0.2\text{Ni}0.2\text{Co}_z\text{P}$ ($z = 0.3, 0.6$ and 1.2) catalyst determined by SEM-EDS and XPS. Constant Ni:Co ratio of 0.5 in the deposition solution ($\text{NiCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.2 mol dm^{-3}), $\text{CoCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.2 mol dm^{-3})).

$c_{\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}} / \text{mol dm}^{-3}$	0.3		0.6		1.2	
	SEM-EDS	XPS	SEM-EDS	XPS	SEM-EDS	XPS
	(At.%)	(At.%)	(At.%)	(At.%)	(At.%)	(At.%)
Ni	39.70	33.3	42.44	19.4	36.31	12.9
Co	52.74	32.7	47.62	25.8	47.28	14.1
P	7.56	34.0	11.11	54.8	16.41	73.0

Electrochemical characterisation

Figure S4: Polarisation curves documenting the influence of NaPO₂H₂·H₂O concentration in the deposition solution on the catalytic activity of the prepared samples, iR corrected. Deposition solution composition: NiCl₂·6H₂O (0.2 mol dm⁻³), CoCl₂·6H₂O (0.2 mol dm⁻³), NaPO₂H₂·H₂O concentration provided in the figure inset.

Experimental conditions: Working RDE (500 rpm, 0.2 mg of catalyst cm⁻²), reference RHE, Ni counter electrode, 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH, 30 °C, 0–10 mA cm⁻², 50 μA cm⁻² s⁻¹, iR corrected.

Figure S5: Tafel plots documenting the influence of NaPO₂H₂·H₂O concentration in the deposition solution on the Tafel slopes of the prepared samples, iR corrected. Constant Ni:Co ratio of 0.5 in the deposition solution.

Experimental conditions: Working RDE (500 rpm, 0.2 mg of catalyst cm⁻²), reference RHE, Ni counter electrode, 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH, 30 °C, 0–10 mA cm⁻², 50 μA cm⁻² s⁻¹, iR corrected.

Influence of the Ni:Co ratio in a deposition solution on the resulting catalyst properties

Figure S6: Changes in surface morphology with respect to increasing Ni:Co ratio in a deposition solution. $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentration of 0.6 mol dm^{-3} . Original SEM-EDS images used for the composition analysis.

The increasing content of Ni leads to a surface morphology change from “sheet-type” ($0.4\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$) to “needle-type” ($0.36\text{Ni}0.04\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$).

Figure S7: XPS analysis of the NiCoP catalyst with respect to increasing Ni:Co ratio in a deposition solution. A – Ni 2p_{3/2} spectra, B – Co 2p spectra, C – P 2p spectra; electrodeposition at -25 mA cm^{-2} , $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Ni and Co total concentration 0.4 mol dm^{-3} , P concentration 0.6 mol dm^{-3} .

Table S3: Elemental composition (At.%) of the $x\text{Ni}_y\text{Co}_z\text{P}$ catalyst determined by SEM-EDS and XPS. Constant $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentration of 0.6 mol dm^{-3} in the deposition solution.

Ni:Co	0		0.1		0.5		0.9	
	SEM-EDS (At.%)	XPS (At.%)	SEM-EDS (At.%)	XPS (At.%)	SEM-EDS (At.%)	XPS (At.%)	SEM-EDS (At.%)	XPS (At.%)
Ni	0.00	0.0	5.88	3.3	36.54	19.4	63.93	57.9
Co	94.23	56.9	87.06	41.5	51.01	25.8	18.53	7.7
P	5.77	43.1	7.07	55.2	11.2	54.8	17.55	34.5

Figure S8: Polarisation curves documenting the influence of the Ni:Co composition in the deposition solution on the catalytic activity of the prepared samples. $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentration of 0.6 mol dm^{-3} in the deposition solution, total concentration of Ni and Co 0.4 mol dm^{-3} .

Experimental conditions: Working RDE (500 rpm, 0.2 mg cm^{-2}), reference RHE, Ni counter electrode, 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KOH, $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $0\text{-}10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, $50 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, *iR* corrected.

Figure S9: Tafel plots documenting the influence of the Ni:Co ratio in the deposition solution on the Tafel slopes of the prepared samples. $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentration of 0.6 mol dm^{-3} in the deposition solution. *Experimental conditions: Working RDE (500 rpm, 0.2 mg cm^{-2}), reference RHE, Ni counter electrode, 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KOH, $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $0\text{-}10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, $50 \text{ } \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, iR corrected.*

Figure S10: Comparison of the Tafel plots of the selected samples. *Experimental conditions: Working RDE (500 rpm, 0.2 mg cm^{-2}), reference RHE, Ni counter electrode, 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KOH, $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $0\text{-}10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, $50 \text{ } \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, iR corrected.*

Performance of the NiCoP/NF cathode under the MAWE conditions

Figure S11: Elemental distribution (Co, P) of the NiCoP catalyst on the Ni foam (cross-section) after different electrodeposition times – 1 min (top row), 15 min (middle row), and 30 min (bottom row).

Only the Co and P spectra are shown in the Figure S11, as the Ni spectrum is affected by the contribution of the Ni foam support. The top, middle, and bottom rows correspond to the electrodeposition times of 1, 15, and 30 minutes, respectively. The top section of each image represents the active part of the electrode in contact with the polymer membrane. The bottom section of the image corresponds to the back of the electrode in contact with the current distributor.

Figure S12: Load curves documenting the influence of the deposition time on the cathode performance in (left) $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KOH}$ and (right) $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KOH}$.

Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; anode (4 cm^2) – $1.5 \text{ mg IrO}_2 \text{ cm}^{-2} + 0.08 \text{ mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm}^{-2}$; cathode (4 cm^2), $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P_Opt/NF}$ or Pt/C (40 wt.%, Johnson-Matthey, UK); KOH electrolyte; temperature – $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Surprisingly, in the less concentrated KOH electrolyte and in the lower voltage region (up to 1.75 V), the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}/\text{NF}$ electrodes obtained after 1 and 30 min of deposition exhibited similar performance. In the higher voltage region, the latter electrode was inferior.

In the 0.1 M KOH electrolyte the concentration of OH^- anions is insufficient to ensure effective ion transport further from the membrane and the reaction occurs mainly at the 2D electrode-membrane interface. Since the catalyst electrodeposition occurs throughout the NF support volume, for the electrode after 30 min of deposition, the catalyst is distributed more in the 3D structure of the NF support. Hence, the active sites not directly in contact with the membrane are utilised. This agrees with the observations in the higher concentrated electrolyte where the concentration of OH^- anions is high and the reaction can occur even deeper in the bulk of the NiCoP/NF electrode. Under such conditions, electrode modified for 30 minutes shows better performance compared to 1 minute deposition.

In both KOH solutions, the cathodes with $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ catalyst outperformed the bare Ni foam cathode. Moreover, in less concentrated KOH solution, the cathode obtained after 15 min of deposition time exhibited better performance than the Ni foam modified by the state-of-the-art Pt/C catalyst (361 mA cm^{-2} vs 321 mA cm^{-2} at 2 V, respectively), see Figure S12.

Figure S13: Load curves documenting the influence of the anode catalyst on the AMWE performance in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KOH (A) and 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH (B). EIS spectra (C) and fitted parameters (D) of the electrolytic cells with different anodes at 1.8 V in 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH solution.

Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; cathode (4 cm^2) – NiCoP_{Opt}/NF (15 min); anode (4 cm^2) – $1.5 \text{ mg IrO}_2 \text{ cm}^{-2} + 0.08 \text{ mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm}^{-2}$; $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KOH}$ electrolyte; temperature – $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, amplitude – 30 mV , frequency range – 10 kHz to 0.1 Hz .

The anode selection plays a significant role in the overall performance of an electrolytic cell and is also critical for understanding the dynamics of cathodic reaction in the water splitting process. For these reasons, the best performing $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}/\text{NF}$ cathode (i.e., after 15 min of electrodeposition) was tested in the laboratory electrolyser with a IrO_2 and non-PGM $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ anode. Predictably, it is evident that the performance of the electrolytic cell with the $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ anode is considerably worse than the cell with the IrO_2/NF anode, especially in the less concentrated KOH solution (82 mA cm^{-2} vs 360 mA cm^{-2} at 2 V). This is primarily caused by the different OER electrocatalytic activity of the anode catalysts used.

To obtain more information on the behaviour of the electrolytic cell under the AWE conditions, the impedance spectra at 1.8 V in a $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KOH}$ solution were recorded and evaluated. Figure S13C shows the comparison of the EIS spectra while evaluated parameters for PGM-based and non-PGM-based anodes are shown in Figure S13D.

To better understand the EIS results and discussion, it is worthy to mention that changing the anode from NiCo_2O_4 to IrO_2 , the current density increased from 0.0862 A cm^{-2} to 0.327 A cm^{-2} , i.e. by 0.241 A cm^{-2} (279 %) at cell voltage 1.8 V in $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KOH}$.

First of all, comparing the results shown in Fig. S13 D, as only the anode differed in the setup, the lower value of ohmic resistance (R_{cell}) of the cell with IrO_2/NF anode can be attributed to a thinner IrO_2 catalyst layer and a higher electronic conductivity of the IrO_2 powder compared to NiCo_2O_4 .

In Figure S13D, it is not possible to address specifically R_p values to anode or cathode reaction, but in the literature, anodic oxygen evolution reaction is typically considered to be slower with higher R_p value when compared to the cathodic hydrogen evolution reaction rate. From **Figure S13D** is clearly seen that $R(p)1$ value is one order of magnitude higher when compared to the $R(p)2$. This suggests that one of the electrode reactions is significantly faster than the second one. Interestingly, when relative decrease of the $R(p)$ values is evaluated for IrO_2 catalyst applied, the similar values of approximately 55 % were achieved for both $R(p)1$ and $R(p)2$. This result is in accordance with the presumption of the controlling reaction. As the slower reaction is accelerated by application of the more active catalyst, the counter reaction is accelerated at the same rate. Additional EIS results showing the cell voltage dependence of the three time-constants are shown in in Figure S14 and Figure S15.

Figure S14: EIS spectra of the $0.04\text{Ni}_{0.36}\text{Co}_{0.9}\text{Co}/\text{NF}$ cathode at different voltages in a 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH solution. Positions R1–R6 shows results of DRT analysis.

Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; anode (4 cm^2) – $1.5 \text{ mg NiCo}_2\text{O}_4 \text{ cm}^{-2} + 0.08 \text{ mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm}^{-2}$; 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH electrolyte; temperature – $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, amplitude – 30 mV , frequency range – 10 kHz to 0.1 Hz .

Figure S15: Dependence of R values on cell voltage. Evaluated from EIS spectra using equivalent electrical circuit.

Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; anode (4 cm^2) – $1.5 \text{ mg NiCo}_2\text{O}_4 \text{ cm}^{-2} + 0.08 \text{ mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm}^{-2}$; 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH electrolyte; temperature – $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, amplitude – 30 mV , frequency range – 10 kHz to 0.1 Hz .

As the polarisation resistance represents a restriction of the charge transfer between the electrode and electrolyte, it is inversely proportional to the applied voltage. If R(pores) were a polarisation resistance, its value would decrease as the cell voltage increased. Figure S15 clearly demonstrates that this was not observed in this case. The independence of R(pores) values on the cell voltage indicates that the resistance R(pores) can be attributed to the double-layer effects of the filled pores of the porous support. Conversely, decreasing values of R(p)1 and R(p)2 with increasing voltage confirm them to be a polarisation resistance.